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A mi padre
Requiescat in pace in aeternum

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

At CERN[14] (Organisation européenne pour la recherche nucléaire), physicists and engineers are probing the fundamental structure of the universe. They use the world's largest and most complex scientific instruments to study the basic constituents of matter — the fundamental particles. The particles are made to collide together at close to the speed of light. The process gives the physicists clues about how the particles interact, and provides insights into the fundamental laws of nature.

The instruments used at CERN are purpose-built particle accelerators and detectors (see Figure 1), for instance the Large Hadron Collider (LHC[9]) is the biggest. Accelerators boost beams of particles to high energies before the beams are made to collide with each other or with stationary targets. Detectors observe and record the results of these collisions. Founded in 1954, the CERN laboratory sits astride the Franco-Swiss border near Geneva. It was one of Europe's first joint ventures and now has 21 member states. CERN is also the birthplace of the World Wide Web. The main site at Meyrin has a large computer facility containing powerful data processing facilities, primarily for experimental data analysis; because of the need to make these facilities available to researchers elsewhere, it has historically been a major wide area networking hub.

Figure 1: CERN accelerator complex

The LHC experiments produce over 30 petabytes of data per year. Archiving vast quantities of data is an essential function at CERN. Magnetic tapes are used as the main long-term storage medium. Often people wonder why CERN still use tape, as it is an old-fashioned technology. Tape is actually a very sophisticated storage material and it can store huge volumes of data. For example, the data which was stored on thousands of reels for the 1990's OPAL[1]¹ experiment now fit on one of today's cartridges. Tape is inexpensive, compact, does not consume much electricity, and is durable for long-term storage. With the data tsunami from the LHC, being able to quickly retrieve petabytes of stored data is essential for physicists to make ground-breaking discoveries.

CERN has more than 300 Petabytes of stored data (the equivalent of 1400 years of full HD-quality movies). Besides tape infrastructure, CERN has a parallel data storage system called EOS[20, 16, 15, 12], a disk-based service providing a low latency storage infrastructure for physics users. The main target area for the service are physics data analysis with use cases often characterised by many concurrent users. CERN IT Storage is the group that ensures a coherent development and operation of the storage services at CERN for all aspects of physics data. The group is divided into three sections: IT-ST-TAB (Tapes, Archives and Backups Section), IT-ST-

¹OPAL was one of the major experiments at CERN before LHC era.

FDO (File systems and Disk Operations Section) and IT-ST-AD (Design and Transitions Section).

The FDO section operates and supports the storage and file system services for physics. I joined the FDO section as Technical Student in 2014 and currently I am a Staff member of the section. My main role is being the Service Manager for CERNBox[16, 15], the CERN biggest cloud storage system. My main activity is to proactively manage the service and the team of twelve people that provides a Dropbox-like solution to more than 17,000 users and 200 institutions with a yearly growth of 400 percent. Other activities involve day-to-day storage operations and end-user support for CERN backbone storage technologies: EOS, CASTOR[4, 3, 22] and CERNBox, managing more than 1,500 servers with more than 60,000 disks, representing about 300 petabyte of data.

This thesis focuses on the design and analysis of the current living system to support a major data migration that will happen in the next months. I decided to take the opportunity to use this activity as the main source for this thesis. The focus of the thesis is the architecture and re-architecture of the systems involved in the CERNBox Service to accommodate the migration. The thesis will not focus on a particular software implementation but rather on high-level design and technological choices to ensure the migration is a success.

1.2 CERNBox and EOS

CERNBox is a cloud synchronisation service for end-users: it allows syncing and sharing files on all major mobile and desktop platforms (Linux, Windows, MacOSX, Android, iOS) aiming to provide offline availability to any data stored in the CERN EOS infrastructure. CERNBox satisfied the high demand in the community for an easily accessible cloud storage solution, an alternative to popular services like Dropbox or Google Drive. Integration of the CERNBox service with the EOS storage back-end was a step forward towards providing 'synchronisation and sharing' capabilities for scientific and engineering use-cases. CERNBox achieved the integration of 'synchronisation and sharing' capabilities with the LHC data analysis tools and transfer services. CERNBox promoted a new integrated way of accessing data for scientific research. The core of CERNBox is a synchronisation and sharing system based on components provided by the ownCloud[18] open software stack. CERNBox provides a service layer on top of storage systems already provided by IT-ST. This allows coherent data access policies to be applied and for service levels compatible with CERN standards to be defined. CERNBox offers various modern ways to access cloud storage (see Figure 2):

Figure 2: High-level view of the main components of CERNBox

- FUSE² access: the storage can be mounted as a filesystem. This is very important for computers inside the computer centre that do not have graphical interfaces but do a lot of batch job processing.
- WebDAV[24, 25, 8]³: the storage is accessible through WebDAV enabled clients like Finder for OSX, Windows Network Drives for Windows or third-party tools like CyberDuck.
- XROOTD[6, 5]⁴: the storage can be accessed through high-optimised

²Filesystem in Userspace is an operating system mechanism for Unix-like computer operating systems that non-privileged users create their own filesystems without editing kernel code. This is achieved by running filesystem code in user space while the FUSE module provides only a bridge to the actual kernel interfaces.

³Web Distributed Authoring and Versioning (WebDAV) is an extension of the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP[7]) that allows clients to perform remote Web content authoring operations.

⁴XRootD software framework is a fully generic suite for fast, low latency and scalable data access, which can serve native any kind of data, organised as a hierarchical filesystem-like namespace, based on the concept of directory

data transfer protocols for doing efficient data analysis.

- Sync client: this is a component, integrated in the user desktop environment, which keeps one (or more) local folders in synchronisation with the central storage server. Users can work on their devices without connectivity and the synchronisation client reconciles changes when the network connectivity is restored. This component is the one that enables the access to offline data with eventual consistency⁵.
- Direct web access: via any web browser the user can upload, download, remove files and share them with other users. Some extensions (available as application plugins in the ownCloud server) provide added functionality such as easing the access to certain types of files (e.g. image viewers).
- Mobile devices: given the fact that most web traffic comes from mobile devices, access to data from these devices is a must. CERNBox provides mobile and tablet applications for Android and IOS.

CERNBox started in 2014 as a pilot service (using NFS storage as backend) which was operated with minimal effort. The service demonstrated a growing demand for file synchronisation and sharing, and reinforced the assumption on the potential popularity of such a service. It was observed a constant increase of the number of users of the pilot service (several tens of new users weekly) both from the physics community and from other communities such as the general laboratory services and the accelerator departments. The type of usage was consequently broad, ranging from the synchronisation of data files (ROOT analysis files), arbitrary work files to office documents shared with colleagues.

The next step was to federate CERNBox with EOS, the CERN disk storage system. This integration effort was the core of my bachelor thesis. The usable capacity at that time of EOS was about 70 PiB with proven capabilities in terms of performance (designed to support LHC analysis) and reliability (geographically distributed replicas). CERNBox then became the main entry point for the entire CERN data store: users selectively access or synchronise data with their devices while their entire data storage is accessible online by the batch jobs for massive data processing or for the creation of large data archives. The choice of EOS allowed for the distribution of

⁵Eventual consistency is a consistency model used in distributed computing to achieve high availability that, informally, guarantees that, if no new updates are made to a given data item, eventually all accesses to that item will return the last updated value.

large user quotas (presently 1 TiB per user). The “disconnected operations” provided by the synchronisation client is an important feature. The synchronisation client could also become a one-way synchronisation agent between the data acquisition and the central services. For example small experiments that need to develop ad-hoc scripts and procedures to upload data from their acquisition system to the CERN central data store: a one-way synchronisation client will be a fundamental simplification. The current client synchronisation behaviour does not yet support this mode (removal of files from the client will remove the same files in the central repository). These are general use cases and are more widely applicable than in the High-Energy Physics workflows. CERNBox can satisfy them in a pretty straightforward way: pictures from surveys in the field, readings of devices or upload of data from a remote machine (sensors, etc).

As stated many times, CERNBox relies on EOS, the CERN disk storage system for correct operation. EOS is an open source distributed disk storage system in production since 2011 at CERN. The development focus has been on low-latency analysis use cases for LHC and non-LHC experiments and data life-cycle management using JBOD hardware for multi Petabyte storage installations. The EOS design implies a split of hot and cold storage and introduced a change of the traditional HSM functionality based workflows at CERN. The 2015 deployment brought storage at CERN to a new scale and foresaw to breach the 100 Petabyte barrier of disk storage in a distributed environment using tens of thousands of (heterogeneous) hard drives. EOS brought to CERN major improvements compared to past storage solutions by allowing quick changes in the quality of service of the storage pools. This allows the data centre to quickly meet the changing performance and reliability requirements of the LHC experiments with minimal data movements and dynamic reconfiguration. For example, the software stack has met the specific needs of the dual computing centre setup required by CERN and allowed the fast design of new workflows accommodating the separation of long-term tape archive and disk storage required for the LHC Run II and future LHC Run III.

Due to the fast growth of the CERNBox service (more than 1 billion files and 7 Petabytes) the EOS software stack started to show some design limitations that heavily impacted the service when this component failed. The EOS version used since 2014 was named Aquamarine, and all the metadata information (file sizes, file paths, checksums, ACLs, ...) was stored in a memory structure, requiring the need to use gold-plated machines with 1 terabyte of RAM for accommodating all this information in RAM. The EOS software also writes the metadata on disk in a journal file in case the software crashes. In the event of a crash, the journal disk-based file is read and every

entry is loaded in memory. With a catalog of more than 1 billion files, the startup time for the service was reaching approximately 2 hours; and when the system crashed the incident affected every single user. These limitations were not acceptable for a major critical service like CERNBox. Due to these limitations, in 2018 the IT-ST team decided to move to a new architecture to reduce the booting time and have a more high-available setup. The idea is to introduce a new architecture and perform a data migration from the old system to the new and developing supporting software and procedures to live with two systems at the same time until the migration is done. These two activities are the main objectives of this thesis.

1.3 Main objectives

The main objective for this thesis is the design of procedures and system architectures to deal with the migration of data from the existing system to a new parallel infrastructure.

- Data migration: The current system is used by approximately 17000 users, contains more than 1 billion files and stores more than 7 petabytes of data. This data needs to be transferred to the new infrastructure in a transparent way to not impact too much user activities.
- Adapt systems to support two parallel systems as one: given that the migration cannot happen in the blink of an eye because of the huge data volume, the migration is going to be a long-running operation that will span several months. For such reason, the existing components need to be adapted to threat the old and new systems as one.

1.4 Planning

Figure 3 shows the expected planning. The project started the 1st of January of 2018 and finished in June 2019. The main activities happen between January 2018 and March 2019. After March the development team implements the designed solution and the migration started in August 2018 and almost finished in January, with residual users to be migrated still appearing in June 2019.

Figure 3: Expected Planning

2 Two architectures

2.1 The limitations of the old system: EOSUSER

The existing CERNBox architecture is depicted in Figure 2 and Figure 4.

Figure 4: Alternative high-level view of the main components of CERNBox

The following components can be observed in the figure:

- EOS, the LHC Disk Storage: EOS is used as the storage for the CERN-Box service. It provides a replicated data store with different ways to access the data: through a FUSE mount, through XROOTD protocol and through the WebDAV protocol. To have the same view from the synchronisation clients, from the web access and from FUSE or XROOTD clients, EOS storage extends the standard WebDAV protocol to include the synchronisation semantics used by ownCloud, therefore a change made using the EOS command line interface, the data dumped by the LHC or the results of an analysis will be synchronised automatically to an end user computer through ownCloud synchronisation clients.
- NGINX⁶ load balancer and Quality of Service Server: NGINX is used to apply some QoS criteria to synchronisation clients, web access, and WebDAV clients. The desktop synchronisation clients and WebDAV pure clients requests are redirected by NGINX directly to EOS to obtain the best performance for data synchronisation. Mobile devices, the

⁶NGINX is a web server which can also be used as a reverse proxy, load balancer, mail proxy and HTTP cache.

web application and Share operations use the ownCloud REST API. As a consequence, these types of requests are redirected to the ownCloud server.

- ownCloud Web Server⁷: the ownCloud stack is used to implement the web server proposed in the advanced model for a synchronisation and share platform. The ownCloud Web Server has a direct connection to EOS thanks to the development of a storage plugin that uses the EOS library to perform operations to EOS in an efficient way.
- ownCloud Desktop Synchronisation Clients: these are the components needed to synchronise automatically the data kept on EOS to the end user local machine. They also allow sharing of local files without having to share through the web application in latest versions.
- ownCloud Mobile Clients: these are the components that allow to access EOS's data from mobiles devices like smartphones and tablets. They do not synchronise data automatically as the storage capacity of these devices is less than the one expected for desktop machines.
- Web Application: the ownCloud server offers a web application to allow universal access to the data from any device anywhere to give an alternative to desktop or mobile applications. The web application also offers a set of highly useful applications like a text editor or an image viewer. As an example of this, a user modifying a text file in the browser will see these changes synchronised to all the enabled clients.
- Native WebDAV Clients: EOS offers a WebDAV interface extended with ownCloud semantics. Therefore, multiple existing DAV clients can be connected to EOS to access the data in a straightforward way. Commonly used clients are the ones already built in the Operative Systems (Finder for MacOSX and Network Drives for Windows) or third-party products like CyberDuck⁸.
- EOS CLI: EOS provides a command line tool to interact with the data and access extra features like trash bin and version support among a vast range of other features. Usually, EOS administrators make heavy

⁷ownCloud is a suite of client-server software for creating and using file hosting services. ownCloud functionally has similarities to the widely used Dropbox.

⁸Cyberduck is an open source client for FTP and SFTP, WebDAV, OpenStack Swift, and Amazon S3, available for Mac OS X and Windows (as of version 4.0) licensed under the GPL.

use of this tool to control EOS' behaviour: configuring replicas, master-slave layouts, setting user quotas or adding more space to the whole cluster.

- **LHC:** the LHC has a lot of services to deal with data dumping when collisions happen in one of the four main detectors (Alice, CMS, Atlas and LHCb). Some of these services dump data directly to EOS to save data at very high speeds. Usually, the LHC dumping services make use of high performance data transfer protocols like XROOTD to write data to EOS.
- **FUSE access:** EOS provides a FUSE interface, so users could mount a particular remote directory in EOS as a local folder in their workstation. The fact of having remote resources in a local folder allows the use of tools for data analysis only work in local file-systems. As a consequence, physicists could use analysis frameworks like ROOT to analyse the raw data that have been dumped from the collisions. This is one of the innovative use cases that CERNBox provides to the scientific community, the ability to interact with high valuable data in a non-disruptive and automatic way.

Figure 5 shows a high level view of the different elements in EOS and their main responsibilities.

Figure 5: High-level view of EOS

The MGM is the component that keeps track of all the information re-

lated with files and directories. It is like the File Allocation Table⁹ in a traditional file-system like FAT32. The MGM stores the location of the files and directories by path, their inodes, sizes, checksums and access control lists among many other attributes. The MGM assigns a unique identifier to every file and directory in the system, this attribute is called the file id (fid) or directory id (pfid).

The FSTs are the servers that store the file contents on the media like HDDs or SSDs. They do not deal with any metadata and they only store the file-contents alongside the fid.

The MQ is a message communication bus using the ZeroMQ[10]¹⁰ technology. This component allows the MGM and FST to communicate in sync/async modes between each other.

Figure 6 shows the relationship between the MGM information in RAM memory and the FST information on the local file-system.

⁹A volume's data area is divided up into identically sized clusters, small blocks of contiguous space. Cluster sizes vary depending on the type of FAT file system being used and the size of the partition; typically cluster sizes lie somewhere between 2 KB and 32 KB.

Each file may occupy one or more of these clusters depending on its size; thus, a file is represented by a chain of these clusters (referred to as a singly linked list). However these clusters are not necessarily stored adjacent to one another on the disk's surface but are often instead fragmented throughout the Data Region.

¹⁰ZeroMQ (ZMQ) is a high-performance asynchronous messaging library, aimed at use in distributed or concurrent applications. It provides a message queue, but unlike message-oriented middleware, a ZeroMQ system can run without a dedicated message broker. The library's API is designed to resemble Berkeley sockets.

Figure 6: MGM and FST knowledge

Figure 7 shows the interaction between a client and EOS in the current installation, named EOSUSER. In the current installation there are two MGMs (one Active and one Passive), similar to a master and slave setup (the slave redirects write operations to the master node).

Figure 7: How EOS works

- A: The client send a request to the management servers with the intention of uploading a file.
- B: The MGM finds an available FST (disk server) that can fit the size

of the file that is going to be uploaded and notifies the client of the location of the disk server.

- C: the client uploads the file directly to the disk server
- D: the disk server communicates with the management node to confirm the upload has been successful or error-ed.

The current system uses the Aquamarine¹¹ version of EOS. As explained before in Section 1, this version stores all information in memory and during the last three years the memory consumption raised to a limit that hardware became very expensive and the booting time very long (see Figures 8 and 9).

Figure 8: EOSUSER memory consumption across years

¹¹<https://github.com/cern-eos/eos/tree/beryl.aquamarine>

Figure 9: EOSUSER boot time across years

2.2 The new EOS architecture: EOSHOME

2.2.1 Eternal booting times

The existing service suffers from very long booting times (almost two hours) of the MGM component. To overcome this limitation a change in technology and structure of the EOS software was needed. For this purpose, a new EOS version code-named Citrine was created. This version of the software introduces radical changes, the major one being the possibility to use different storage drivers to store the catalog information. After looking at different technologies to satisfy the requirements of storing more than 1 terabyte of RAM information on persistent storage and being performant enough the following technologies were evaluated:

- **RocksDB:** is a high performance embedded database for key-value data. It is a fork of LevelDB by Facebook optimized to exploit many central processing unit (CPU) cores, and make efficient use of fast storage, such as solid-state drives (SSD), for input/output (I/O) bound workloads. It is based on a log-structured merge-tree (LSM tree[19]) data structure. It is written in C++ and provides official application programming interface (API) language bindings for C++, C, and Java; alongside many third-party language bindings. RocksDB is open-source software, and was originally released under a BSD 3-clause license. However, in July 2017 the project was migrated to a dual license of both Apache 2.0 and GPLv2 license, possibly in response to the Apache Software Foundation's blacklist of the previous BSD+Patents license clause. RocksDB

is used in production systems at various web-scale enterprises including Facebook, Yahoo!, and LinkedIn.

- Redis: Remote Dictionary Server is an in-memory data structure project implementing a distributed, in-memory key-value database with optional durability. Redis supports different kinds of abstract data structures, such as strings, lists, maps, sets, sorted sets, HyperLogLogs[2], bitmaps, streams, and spatial indexes. The project is mainly developed by Salvatore Sanfilippo and as of 2019, is sponsored by Redis Labs. It is open-source software released under a BSD 3-clause license.
- Raft: is a consensus algorithm designed as an alternative to Paxos[13]. It was meant to be more understandable than Paxos by means of separation of logic, but it is also formally proven safe and offers some additional features. Raft offers a generic way to distribute a state machine across a cluster of computing systems, ensuring that each node in the cluster agrees upon the same series of state transitions. It has a number of open-source reference implementations, with full-specification implementations in Go, C++, Java, and Scala. It is named after Reliable, Replicated, Redundant, And Fault-Tolerant.

Based on these three technologies the EOS team developed a component called QuarkDB[21]: a highly available data store that implements a small subset of the REDIS protocol that persists data using RocksDB and brings high-availability, resiliency and fault tolerance thanks to the Raft consensus algorithm.

Figure 10 shows the relationship between components in the new architecture (see Figure 6 for the old).

Figure 10: EOS Citrine component relationship

- **MGM:** in the previous deployment (Figure 6), this component was the source of truth for the whole system and contained all metadata information stored in memory. Now, this component acts as a cache for the metadata, caching metadata from the QuarkDB node. The entries in memory expire after a configurable TTL (Time to Live).
- **FST:** the disk server stays as before and its sole responsibility is not changed: store file contents.
- **QuarkDB Node:** this component is now the source of truth for the entire system. The metadata does not live in memory anymore but is

stored in a RocksDB database on SSDs for high-performance. Despite the performance downgrade from RAM memory to SSDs, the MGM can communicate to various QuarkDB nodes concurrently, increasing the metadata throughput over a distributed set of nodes.

Figure 11 shows the interaction between the previous components:

Figure 11: EOS component interaction in Citrine version with QuarkDB Cluster

- A: The client send a request to the management servers with the intention of uploading a file.
- B: the MGM contacts the QuarkDB Node to obtain the location of an FST that can fit the data being uploaded.
- C: the location of the FST is being sent to the MGM, that can cache the FST location based on the configurable caching strategies.

- D: The client uploads the file directly to the disk server
- D: the disk server communicates with the management node to confirm the upload has been successful or error-ed, which then connects to QuarkDB to commit this information.

2.2.2 Single-failure domain

The existing system has a single-failure domain: the MGM (management) node. Once this component crashes, 17K users cannot work as the system needs to reboot and it takes a lot of time as explained in Section 2.2.1.

Section 3 explains how the data migration will happen between the old (EOSUSER) and new (EOSHOME) backend storage systems for CERNBox. For the design of the new system, one of the requirements is that is high-available, and one way to increase the system availability is to have multiple failure domains. For this purpose, the new system uses a technique known as sharding¹² The system is horizontally split in 24 logical EOS systems, the sharding is based on the first letter of the username, therefore one shard per letter of the alphabet.

Figure 12 shows the logical view of the EOSHOME system.

¹²A database shard is a horizontal partition of data in a database or search engine. Each individual partition is referred to as a shard or database shard. Each shard is held on a separate database server instance, to spread load. Some data within a database remains present in all shards,[notes 1] but some appears only in a single shard. Each shard (or server) acts as the single source for this subset of data.

Figure 12: EOSHOME initial architecture

This initial architecture exposes all EOS system to the client which is not convenient, as the client now has to perform more logic to guess where a file should be uploaded based on the path. This architecture also has the flaw that any further split of the system will need a re-configuration of all clients. For example, if the instance EOSHOME-A starts to get full, a split can be done into EOSHOME-A0 and EOSHOME-A1, but the clients will need to be updated and incorporate new redirection logic. This design increases the cost of maintainability and pushes undesired logic to the clients.

Figure 13 shows the desired architecture.

Figure 13: EOSHOME desired architecture

In this architecture the client only needs to know one component that will incorporate all the sharing logic. A client that wishes to talk to the system will need to query this component first to understand where the data should be located (A). Then, the client will redirect the request to the given system given by the redirector to finalise the operation (B). The client can implement some smart caching techniques to not query the EOS Redirector for every request and therefore reducing network latency to increase throughput in consecutive operations.

3 Data migration

The migration will consist of moving data from the old system (EOSUSER, see Figure 7) and the new system (EOSHOME, see Figure 13).

The volume of data to be migrated is in the order of 7 petabytes of data, so the migration needs to be transparent for the end-user as it will span several months.

Figure 14 shows a table with some common data volumes to be transferred using different network connection settings.

Data Size	Close Far						
	100 Gbps	10 Gbps	1 Gbps	100 Mbps	10 Mbps	1 Mbps	
100 PB	124 days	3 years	34 years	340 years	3,404 years	34,048 years	
10 PB	12 days	124 days	3 years	34 years	340 years	3,404 years	
1 PB	30 hours	12 days	124 days	3 years	34 years	340 years	
100 TB	3 hours	30 hours	12 days	124 days	3 years	34 years	
10 TB	18 minutes	3 hours	30 hours	12 days	124 days	3 years	
1 TB	2 minutes	18 minutes	3 hours	30 hours	12 days	124 days	
100 GB	11 seconds	2 minutes	18 minutes	3 hours	30 hours	12 days	
10 GB	1 second	11 seconds	2 minutes	18 minutes	3 hours	30 hours	
1 GB	0.1 seconds	1 second	11 seconds	2 minutes	18 minutes	3 hours	
	100 Gbps	10 Gbps	1 Gbps	100 Mbps	10 Mbps	1 Mbps	

Figure 14: Cloud transfer speeds

This table can be found at Google Cloud¹³. The time it will take to move 7 petabytes of data will be around 84 days using a 10gb network link. The prediction is based on pure network traffic without taking into account any overhead given by the software, assuming disk bandwidth is always available at 100 % and that errors do not happen. Neither of these three conditions apply to CERNBox as the software brings overheads for reading/writing files across two instances. Oftentimes, the disks are under high-load as the system cannot be stopped from user-activity, which results in long IO waits for accessing the contents of a disk.

¹³<https://cloud.google.com/solutions/transferring-big-data-sets-to-gcp>

To have some margin based on the characteristics of the system, the migration is planned for 6 months.

3.1 Syncing data from EOSUSER to EOSHOME

Having set the migration scope for 6 months, the next step is to find the best way to transfer the data over the network. In Section 1, it was mentioned that EOS has the capability to be accessed using a FUSE file-system. A FUSE file-system is nothing else than having a remote storage system mounted as a local folder in the computer, the only difference between a FUSE and other ways of mounting remote storage is just an implementation detail. A FUSE program lives in user-space¹⁴ while others live in kernel-space as kernel modules¹⁵. The FUSE implementation is easier as the software has access to high-level libraries and crashing does not put the whole system into a halt. On the other hand, having a kernel-module to mount a remote storage allows for the maximum degree of optimization as there are not context switchers between user-land and kernel space. Traditionally, file-system software developments start with FUSE implementations until they get stable enough to move to a kernel module for further optimization. The EOS software suite contains a FUSE implementation that can be installed on any Unix-based system like Linux or Mac OS.

CERNBox had a previous migration done in 2015 when the service was using NFS[11?] filers¹⁶ and the pilot data was transfer to the existing system using FUSE and RSYNC[23]¹⁷ to move the data.

¹⁴The term user-land (or user space) refers to all code that runs outside the operating system's kernel. User-land usually refers to the various programs and libraries that the operating system uses to interact with the kernel: software that performs input/output, manipulates file system objects, application software, etc.

¹⁵In computing, a loadable kernel module (LKM) is an object file that contains code to extend the running kernel, or so-called base kernel, of an operating system. LKMs are typically used to add support for new hardware (as device drivers) and/or file-systems, or for adding system calls. When the functionality provided by a LKM is no longer required, it can be unloaded in order to free memory and other resources.

¹⁶Network File System (NFS) is a distributed file system protocol originally developed by Sun Microsystems in 1984, allowing a user on a client computer to access files over a computer network much like local storage is accessed. NFS, like many other protocols, builds on the Open Network Computing Remote Procedure Call (ONC RPC) system. The NFS is an open standard defined in Request for Comments (RFC), allowing anyone to implement the protocol.

¹⁷rsync is a utility for efficiently transferring and synchronizing files between a computer and an external hard drive and across networked computers by comparing the modification times and sizes of files. It is commonly found on Unix-like operating systems. The rsync algorithm is a type of delta encoding, and is used for minimizing net-

Based on the positive result of that migration, the new migration will rely again on this software stack. RSYNC does not only allow for an efficient data transfer, but also protects the transfer of the data by computing the MD5 checksum¹⁸ on the fly.

Figure 15 shows the setup for the data migration. In this setup, a server is configured to mount using FUSE both the old system (EOSUSER) under the /user directory and the new system (EOSHOME) under various directories /home-a, /home-b and so on.

work usage. Zlib may be used for additional data compression, and SSH or stunnel can be used for security.

¹⁸The MD5 message-digest algorithm is a widely used hash function producing a 128-bit hash value. Although MD5 was initially designed to be used as a cryptographic hash function, it has been found to suffer from extensive vulnerabilities. It can still be used as a checksum to verify data integrity, but only against unintentional corruption. It remains suitable for other non-cryptographic purposes, for example for determining the partition for a particular key in a partitioned database.

Figure 15: Data migration setup

Figure 16 shows the migration process happening across the different directories using RSYNC. An important feature of RSYNC is that is harmless to run it multiple times against the same data set. Thanks to this, data can be copied in the background and when the user is ready to be migrated a final delta RSYNC copy can be done. RSYNC does not transfer the whole data set every time is run, on the contrary, it has very smart delta transfer algorithm that only copies files that have changed or are new. Moreover, RSYNC only copy the bytes that have changed and not the whole contents, therefore the name of delta encoding. The ability to run multiple gradual RSYNCS allows the data transfer to be almost transparent.

For the final copy is needed that the client stop writing in the system to

the copy can happen and the data set from the old system will be the same on the new. To achieve this to happen, client activity is paused until the final delta is done. The final delta can last a few seconds to a few minutes, it will depend on the amount of data the user has created since the last RSYNC copy happened.

Figure 16: RSYNC copy

3.2 Metadata migration

Data is important but so is metadata. Although RSYNC supports the copy of file-system extended attributes¹⁹, it doesn't have support to copy EOS metadata, that is very specific to this technology.

¹⁹Extended file attributes are file system features that enable users to associate computer files with metadata not interpreted by the file-system, whereas regular attributes have a purpose strictly defined by the file-system (such as permissions or records of creation and modification times). Unlike forks, which can usually be as large as the maximum file size, extended attributes are usually limited in size to a value significantly

This is the list of some additional metadata found on files and directories in EOS:

- `sys.acl`: defines an ACL (Access Control List): ACLs are defined only on the directory level via this extended attribute (set by admins) and `user.acl` (set by end-users). A rule is defined in the following way:

```
<rule> = u:<uid|username>|g:<gid|groupname>|egroup:<name>|z::{ rwxomqci (!d)(+d)(!u)(+u)
```

A rule has three colon separated fields. It starts with the type of rule: User (u), Group (g), eGroup²⁰ (egroup) or all (z). The second field specifies the name or the unix ID²¹ of user/group rules and the eGroup name for eGroups. The last field contains the rule definition. Some of the permissions available are the following:

- r: grants read permission
- w: grants write permissions
- x: grants browsing permission
- m: grants change mode permission
- !m: forbids change mode operations
- !d: forbids deletion of files and directories
- +d: overwrites a ‘!d’ rule and allow deletion of files and directories
- !u: forbids update of files
- +u: overwrites a ‘!u’ rule and allow updates for files
- q: grants ‘set quota’ permissions on a quota node
- c: grants ‘change owner’ permission on directory children
- i: sets the immutable flag

smaller than the maximum file size. Typical uses include storing the author of a document, the character encoding of a plain-text document, or a checksum, cryptographic hash or digital certificate, and discretionary access control information.

²⁰E-groups are multi-purpose groups which can for instance be used as email address (optionally with mailing list functionality) or as NICE group to give/restrict access to computing resources.

²¹Unix-like operating systems identify a user by a value called a user identifier, often abbreviated to user ID or UID. The UID, along with the group identifier (GID) and other access control criteria, is used to determine which system resources a user can access. The password file maps textual user names to UIDs. UIDs are stored in the inodes of the Unix file system, running processes, tar archives, and the now-obsolete Network Information Service. In POSIX-compliant environments, the command-line command `id` gives the current user’s UID, as well as more information such as the user name, primary user group and group identifier (GID).

- `sys.allow.oc.sync`: enables ownCloud synchronisation in the directory. When enabled, EOS will propagate modification times and ETAGs²² from the modified resource (directory or file) to the furthest ancestor in the tree that has this attribute set (see Figure 17).
- `sys.forced.atomic`: if present enforces atomic uploads e.g. files appear only when their upload is complete. The atomic upload is triggered by an atomic rename from a temporary file.
- `sys.forced.blocksize`: enforces the use of a block-size for reading and writing files: 4k,64k,128k,256k or 1M.
- `sys.forced.checksum`: enforces the use of file-level checksums: `adler32`²³, `md5` or `sha1`.
- `sys.forced.layout`: enforces a particular replication mode for the files like plain replication or erasure encoding²⁴
- `sys.versioning`: defines the maximum number of file versions when a file gets modified.

²²The ETag or entity tag is part of HTTP, the protocol for the World Wide Web. It is one of several mechanisms that HTTP provides for Web cache validation, which allows a client to make conditional requests. This allows caches to be more efficient and saves bandwidth, as a Web server does not need to send a full response if the content has not changed. ETags can also be used for optimistic concurrency control,[1] as a way to help prevent simultaneous updates of a resource from overwriting each other.

²³Adler-32 is a checksum algorithm which was invented by Mark Adler in 1995, and is a modification of the Fletcher checksum. Compared to a cyclic redundancy check of the same length, it trades reliability for speed (preferring the latter). Adler-32 is more reliable than Fletcher-16, and slightly less reliable than Fletcher-32.

²⁴In coding theory, an erasure code is a forward error correction (FEC) code under the assumption of bit erasures (rather than bit errors), which transforms a message of k symbols into a longer message (code word) with n symbols such that the original message can be recovered from a subset of the n symbols.

Figure 17: Propagation of mtimes and etags in the file-system tree

These attributes must be migrated alongside the data. For such purpose the idea will be to set them every time the rsync data migration happens.

To reduce the risk of metadata inconsistencies, a metadata verification script will be run using WebDAV to compute the differences between the previous and the new system (see Figure 18).

```

PROPFIND remote.php/dav/files/gonzalhu/university-tfm
<?xml version="1.0"?>
<propfind xmlns:d="DAV:" xmlns:oc="http://owncloud.org/ns">
  <prop>
    <getlastmodified />
    <getetag />
    <getcontenttype />
    <resourceType />
    <oc:fileid />
    <oc:permissions />
    <oc:size />
    <getcontentlength />
    <oc:tags />
    <oc:favorite />
    <oc:owner-display-name />
    <oc:share-types />
  </prop>
</propfind>

<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<multistatus xmlns:d="DAV:" xmlns:oc="http://owncloud.org/ns" xmlns:s="http://sabredav.org/ns">
  <response>
    <d:href>/remote.php/dav/files/gonzalhu/university-tfm/</d:href>
    <d:propstat>
      <prop>
        <resourceType />
        <collection />
      </d:resourceType>
      <d:getcontentlength>4</d:getcontentlength>
      <d:getcontenttype>httpd/unix-directory</d:getcontenttype>
      <d:getlastmodified>Sat, 15 Jun 2019 09:55:51 UTC</d:getlastmodified>
      <d:getetag>19d3314:1560592551:457</d:getetag>
      <oc:fileid>home:27079444</oc:fileid>
      <oc:downloadURL />
      <oc:dDC />
      <oc:permissions>WCKDNVR</oc:permissions>
    </d:prop>
    <d:status>HTTP/1.1 200 OK</d:status>
  </d:propstat>
  </d:response>
  <d:response>
    <d:href>/remote.php/dav/files/gonzalhu/university-tfm/tfm.tex</d:href>
    <d:propstat>
      <prop>
        <resourceType />
        <d:getcontentlength>4</d:getcontentlength>
        <d:getcontenttype>application/x-tex</d:getcontenttype>
        <d:getlastmodified>Sat, 15 Jun 2019 09:55:51 UTC</d:getlastmodified>
        <d:getetag>"65281157310185472:03d001a1"</d:getetag>
        <oc:fileid>home:65281157310185472</oc:fileid>
        <oc:downloadURL />
        <oc:dDC />
        <oc:permissions>WCKDNVR</oc:permissions>
      </d:prop>
      <d:status>HTTP/1.1 200 OK</d:status>
    </d:propstat>
  </d:response>
</multistatus>

```

Figure 18: Metadata consistency check using WebDAV

4 Tales of two living systems

Once the migration is started there will be two systems living together in a production environment. The current software needs to be adapted to support a transparent operation from the end-user perspective.

The current architecture is shown already in Figure 2. The following sections will explain how to support transparent interactions between the two systems based on the access protocol.

A prerequisite before deciding what tricks to use for the transparent re-directions is to find how to decide if a user is migrated or not.

4.1 Transparent FUSE access

FUSE access both to the old and the new system is done transparently using file-system symbolic links²⁵. When the user is migrated a symbolic link is

²⁵In computing, a symbolic link (also sym-link or soft link) is a term for any file that contains a reference to another file or directory in the form of an absolute or relative path and that affects path-name resolution.

created from the old system to the new, as it is the kernel that deals with the redirection.

Figure 19: FUSE soft-link

4.2 XROOTD access

To allow transparent access to native-xrootd clients the idea will be to use a new machine that will redirect the client to the correct place. This machine is available in the XROOTD framework as another component. Figure 20 shows the desired architecture.

Figure 20: XROOTD Redirector

The XROOTD redirector is a server that can be configured by rules to redirect paths to other servers.

- A: the user zacarias wants to list the contents of his home directory and contacts the xrootd redirector server.
- B: the server contains rules to redirect paths to other instances. In this

case, the path `/eos/user/z/zacarias` is redirected to the server `eoshome-z.cern.ch`.

- C: the client connects directly to the final server.

4.3 HTTP access

Figure 21 shows the flow that happens when a user is migrated.

Figure 21: CERNBox migration flow chart

- NM: during the Non-Migrated status the RSYNC data backup and the metadata synchronisation happen in the background. When the user is ready to transfer to the OM state, 99% of the work is already done.

- OM: during the Ongoing-Migration phase the access to the system is closed to the user. A last delta RSYNC happen to ensure recently modified files are taken into account. The last step in this phase is to perform the WebDAV metadata verification step (refer to Section 3.2). If this step is successful the user is finally migrated. If there is an error in this phase, the user needs to be set back to the Non-Migrated status as leaving the user in OM would not allow users to access their data.
- Migrated: users in this state have been granted access to the new system and forbidden to access the old system.

The database is a critical component in the migration as a wrong migration status can cause the user to not being able to access the system or cause data loss. To ensure a reliable migration the database needs to be persisted using a technology that will grant also a high performance access to the information.

In the current system the throughput in terms of requests per second hitting the server is around 400 Hz with peaks to 4KHz (see Figure 22).

Figure 22: Typical HTTP throughput in CERNBox

This rate will need to be sustained by the technology responsible for storing the migration database. Basically, the database behind will need to be able to persist the data, allow concurrent access to the database and be able to sustain the previous load. Based on previous experience running Redis services for internal CERNBox component for caching purposes, Redis will be used as the database to store the migration information. Redis serves data from an internal in-memory structure, which makes Redis blazing fast to serve requests. Persistence is achieved in Redis in two ways:

- RDB persistence: performs point-in-time snapshots of the Redis dataset at specified intervals.
- AOF persistence: logs every write operation received by the server, that will be played again at server startup, reconstructing the original data set. Commands are logged using the same format as the Redis protocol itself, in an append-only fashion. Redis is able to rewrite the log on background when it gets too big.

The main advantage of RDB is that is a simple persistence layer that trades off durability for performance as the snapshots are created at time intervals, increasing data loss risk if a power outage happens in this time period. AOF trades of performance for durability using an append-only file, that is fsynced²⁶ every time a new record is written into Redis. The persistence layer will be RDB and to minimize data loss a Redis cluster using a Master-Slave setup will be setup. Figure 23 shows the desired Redis deployment.

Figure 23: Redis setup for migration

The number of READ operations is orders of magnitude bigger than the expected number of write operations (setting migration status). This setup has the advantage that READ operations can also be load balanced across the two nodes.

To allow transparent access from HTTP there are two possible options:

²⁶sync is a standard system call in the Unix operating system, which commits all data in the kernel file-system to non-volatile storage buffers, i.e., data which has been scheduled for writing via low-level I/O system calls. Higher-level I/O layers such as stdio may maintain separate buffers of their own.

- Adapt the PHP-software stack based on ownCloud to handle two underlying storage backends.
- Introduce a new proxy that will deal with the migration logic and leave the existing software as it is.

The first option has the advantage that there is no need to introduce a new component to perform the redirection logic but has the disadvantage the the code base will become more complex and difficult to maintain. Introducing a new proxy server will add latency to the system as there will be another network hop.

Figure 24: Alternatives to handle transparent HTTP access

In the scenario A the ownCloud PHP-based application is adapted so every time there is request for the storage, the logged-in username is check against the Redis database. In the user is migrated the request is sent to the new storage system, else to the old one. The keys stored in Redis are paths to the user home-directory, so if user "andres" is migrate the Redis key will be "/eos/user/a/andres". This option has the drawback that PHP is an interpreted language and therefore every bootstrapping code needs to be re-evaluated every time a request is handled.

In the scenario B, a new layer 7 proxy according to the OSI standard²⁷. The proxy is an HTTP proxy that understand application logic, that is that can extract user information from the request URL and proxy the request accordingly to the corresponding storage server. Existing proxies like NGINX or Apache are application-agnostic and they only perform proxy logic on HTTP standard elements but they do not understand application specific logic. For such reason, it would be necessary to develop a layer 7 HTTP proxy that understand the application logic. The programming language for such server would be Go as it is a modern programming language for systems and the one adopted by the CERNBox team for developing systems.

For simplicity, the option B (layer 7 proxy) will be the one used as it is simpler to operate and it can serve for further ad-hoc developments in the future.

4.4 The final architecture

Figure 25 shows the desired architecture for the migration.

²⁷The application layer is the OSI layer closest to the end user, which means both the OSI application layer and the user interact directly with the software application. This layer interacts with software applications that implement a communicating component.

Figure 25: Final desired architecture

- A: during the A phase, the data migration server copies data from the old system to the new using RSYNC as explained in Section 3.
- B1: Once the migration is finished, the XROOTD redirector is updated with new redirection information for the concerned user.
- B2: Once the migration is finished, the Redis migration database is updated, setting the key for the user as "migrated".
- B3: Once the migration is finished, the old directory is renamed to a hidden folder and a symbolic link is created to the new system. Steps B1, B2 and B3 need to happen as atomically as possible.
- C: when a client access using the XROOTD protocol, a redirection will happen to the new system if the user is migrated.
- D: when a client access using HTTP(S) it will be proxied to the new system if migrated.

- E: when a client access via FUSE, the symbolic link will transparently forward the operation to the other file-system.

4.5 The power of DNS

To make the migration as transparent as possible the use of DNS[17]²⁸ is needed. The clients of the system connect to a DNS alias than points to a particular IP address. This is achieved by A (for ipv4) and AAAA (for ipv6) records.

Figure 26 shows the current and new DNS configurations. The class in IN (Internet) as the service in exposed in public Internet. The TTL (Time To Live) is 60 seconds. The TTL specifies for how long a client can cache the DNS entry before flushing it. A small value like 60 seconds allows for a fast update of the clients. A smaller value will mean the DNS servers will get hit hardly as the DNS records cannot be cached for enough time. A larger TTL will make clients sending requests to the decommissioned server as the DNS propagation will take time.

Both eosuser.cern.ch and cernbox.cern.ch are DNS sub-zones and they are managed by their own zone file. A more high available setup is to use CNAME records to another DNS aliases but this is not possible with apex domains inside a DNS Zone File even tough there are domain providers that violate this section of the DNS standard.

²⁸The Domain Name System is a hierarchical decentralized naming system for computers, services, or other resources connected to the Internet or a private network. It associates various information with domain names assigned to each of the participating entities

Figure 26: DNS Configuration

5 Time skip

After designing the new architecture and implemented the required software components by the development team, the migration started on the first half of June 2018 with test users and in the 1st of August opened for full throttle.

Figure 27 shows the migration during the last year period. At the beginning of June 2018 the number of files on the old system was around 600 million. On the first of August the migration started and the 5 new physical machines started to get the load.

Figure 27: Data migration over time

Previous figures 12 and 13 mentioned 24 instances, one per letter, but that is the logical layout. Every physical machine contains around 5 letters to distribute the load and have more density of users per machine as the cost of having 24 machines for better redundancy was out of order. In January 2019 a deletion campaign started on the old system and it was visible on February 2019. The current new system accommodates new users that arrive to CERN and almost all the users of the previous system. In June 2019 the number of users in the old system are 140 and they are being manually migrated as the migration scripts fail to perform the migration due to complex home directory structures. By June 2019 the sum of files in the new system is around 660 million files and 326 million files in the old system.

The old system is also used for collaborative work-spaces aka "Project Spaces"; that is the reason that after triggering the cleaning campaign the number of files did not reach zero.

In Section 3 it was decided that the migration should take 6 months but in reality took 7. The causes for this delay were various, most notably peak loads that made the data transfer slower. Figure 28 shows the aggregated disk IO (reads and writes) across the whole cluster. At the end of October is clearly visible a drop of IO performance in the source system for read operations that result in slow transfer speeds.

Figure 28: Disk IO over time

5.1 Issues found

During the migration there were some issues found that required fixes of the migration software on the spot, the following list contains the most notorious ones:

- **Character encoding:** during the migration of different home directories some paths contained "weird" characters, in UTF-8[26]²⁹ terms, extended runes. The encoding of the paths done in client side is left to the user application and the migration software was failing to copy some files to the target system. After analysis of the anomaly, it was found that the EOS storage system was not enforcing UTF-8 for storing the character set, basically allowing any byte sequence to be stored. Already copied paths with the wrong character set were analyzed to guess the source encoding (Latin, ASCII, ...) and trans-coded to UTF-8.
- **Failed synchronization:** when performing the delta RSYNC to have a final synchronization between the old and the new system there were some failures because of some data timing out to be copied. Sometimes because the software was hanging, sometimes because a disk was broken (CERNBox has disk failures every day), sometimes because of software bug. This problem was annoying as the access to the system was closed to the user, then restored, then closed again until the migration and bugs were fixed.

²⁹UTF-8 is a variable width character encoding capable of encoding all 1,112,064 valid code points in Unicode using one to four 8-bit bytes. The encoding is defined by the Unicode standard, and was originally designed by Ken Thompson and Rob Pike. The name is derived from Unicode Transformation Format 8-bit

- Millions of files inside a single directory: some users (or applications) are not well educated and they create millions of files inside a single directory, therefore putting the storage system on fire as listing such a big tree can consume a lot of memory and resources. The users that are still to be migrated they suffer from this issue. The workaround is to partition the data into different sub-directories based on some bucket algorithm.

5.2 Outlook

During the design process of the migration of one of the most critical IT services at CERN I had the opportunity to put in place many of the topics covered in various subjects at the university, specially the ones related with systems architecture and systems design. During this process I took the opportunity to document my thought process and write up this doc. During this exercise I learned that no matter how well you plan, you will always have to react to unknown deviations and deal with them. We are planning the migration of a second system at CERN and will re-use the architecture I designed, let's see what are the new challenges in the horizon.

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